

Nucleic Acid Delivery to Retinal Cells using Lipopeptides as a Potential Tool towards Ocular Gene Therapies

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ABSTRACT

We evaluated the use of lipopeptides capable to bind to nucleic acids towards plasmid DNA (pDNA) delivery. The investigations were particularly focused on arising retinal pigment epithelial cells (ARPE-19) as motivated by the considerable number of ocular disorders linked to gene aberrations. The lipopeptides comprised the artificial oligoamino acid succinyl-tetraethylene pentamine (Stp) as well as incorporated lysines, histidines, cysteines, fatty acids, and tyrosine trimers. Regardless of the structural differences, the lipopeptides demonstrated to efficiently condense pDNA at nitrogen-to-phosphate molar ratio (N/P) ≥ 6 . Spheric nanoparticles were observed by cryo-TEM and dynamic light scattering determined hydrodynamic sizes ranging from 50-130 nm. The biological assays evidenced highly efficient pDNA delivery with a lower degree of cytotoxicity compared to the well-known transfecting agent linear polyethylenimine (LPEI). Although more efficient than LPEI, cysteine-containing carriers were demonstrated to be less efficient than the other counterparts possibly due to exceeding polyplex stabilization *via* disulfide cross links, which could hamper pDNA unpacking at the target site. Therefore, clearly a balance between complex stability and cargo release should be taken into account to optimize the transfection efficiency of the non-viral vectors. The gene transfer activity in ARPE-19 cells suggests the applicability of this kind of carrier for ocular treatments based on retinal gene delivery.

INTRODUCTION

The intracellular delivery of nucleic acids can be used in gene therapies in order to substitute inactive or abnormal genes. This approach has potential towards the treatment of a variety of diseases.^{1,2} Due to the high molecular weight and polarity, as well as the negative nature of nucleic acids and plasma membranes, thus leading to electrostatic repulsions, an efficient intracellular delivery of naked DNA is challenging.³ Additionally, naked genes are susceptible to nuclease attack and rapid clearance whenever in biological environments.^{4,5} These issues motivated the use of viral vectors able to provide efficient cellular uptake and therapeutic activity inside cells.^{6,7} The use of viral vectors is nevertheless sometimes associated to downsides including insertional mutagenesis, genotoxicity and immunogenicity.⁸ Furthermore, the limited loading capacity in terms of nucleic acid size ($M_w < 4.5$ kDa) for instance, for adeno-associated virus (AAV),⁹ precludes its use in the treatment of diseases associated with larger genes. Additionally, the very high production cost is currently incompatible with the society financial means.¹⁰ These drawbacks stimulated the development of alternative platforms and the research on non-viral vectors.¹¹ The scientific investigations in this regards are currently dominated by lipids¹² and cationic polymers¹³⁻¹⁵ which are able to interact electrostatically with the negatively charged phosphate groups of the nucleic acid, thereby leading to the formation of electrostatic complexes. Indeed, the use of cationic liposome/DNA (lipoplexes) and cationic polymer/DNA (polyplexes) for the transfer of genes into somatic cells is popular since they are rather stable, can be designed to be relatively safe, cost effective and do also provide advantages regarding scalability and quality control.¹⁶ Nevertheless, the transfection rates do not compete with that of viral vectors which are in general more efficient.^{17,18} Furthermore, due to membrane disruptive properties, non-viral vectors, particularly polycations, can be cytotoxic.^{19,20} Accordingly, advances in vector

engineering and delivery technologies still have to be considered in order to overcome particularly the safety-efficacy dilemma.

In this framework, sequence-defined oligo(ethanamino) amides (OAAs) based on artificial oligoamino acids and solid phase-assisted peptide synthesis (SPPS) have been developed as a versatile delivery platform.²¹ Such molecules combine the advantages of aminoethylene-based polymers with the chemical precision of peptides. The further incorporation of fatty acids (lipo-OAAs) was demonstrated to enhance the intracellular delivery of genetic material due to increased polyplex stability and enhanced membranolytic activity.^{22,23} The lipopolyplex stabilization could be further increased *via* the coupling of terminal cysteine residues to the sequences due to the formation of bioreducible disulfide bridges,^{21,24} as well as by the addition of tyrosine trimers resulting in π - π stacking noncovalent interactions.²⁴ Furthermore, the buffering capacity of such type of gene carrier could be augmented by the coupling of histidine domains, thus boosting endosomal escape.²⁵⁻²⁹

In the past, such platforms have been utilized for the delivery of diverse types of biomacromolecules, including siRNA,^{22,30} pDNA,^{23,28,31,32} mRNA,³³ splice-switching oligonucleotides³⁴ and proteins.³⁵ Further investigations concerning particularly the intranuclear delivery of plasmid DNA in a wider library of cell lines is certainly relevant. Amongst the wide range of diseases that can be treated using gene therapies, cancer is the most common, counting for roughly 2/3 of the ongoing clinical trials.³⁶ Monogenetic and cardiovascular diseases are also frequently considered.³⁷ Such an approach is also envisaged to treat, typically rare, genetic-related eye disorders.³⁸ Truly, the treatment options are limited to target retinal gene mutations such as, for instance, retinitis pigmentosa, Stargardt disease and Leber congenital amaurosis, to name a few.^{39,40} Since the eye is compartmentalized, the localized delivery of therapeutics potentially minimizes unwanted side effects. Many ocular genetic diseases are linked to aberrations in the retinal pigment epithelium, a monolayer of

cuboidal cells lining the back of the eye. These cells are difficult to be transfected since the tight junctions hamper the penetration of large macromolecules and self-assemblies. This motivated us to conduct this investigation using the ARPE-19 (arising retinal pigment epithelial) and a second well-known cell line (HeLa) for comparison purposes. Despite the encouraging outputs regarding the use of recombinant adeno-associated virus (AAVs) in ocular gene therapies, including marketed products such as Luxturna (gene therapy that uses a AAV2 viral vector to deliver the human RPE65 cDNA into retinal cells),⁴¹ expanding the available repertoire of gene carriers is highly relevant to provide qualified information and a wider library of delivery agents. Polymer- and peptide-based systems were demonstrated to be potentially useful in the delivery of genetic material to retinal cells⁴²⁻⁴⁵ nevertheless, the applicability of artificial lipopeptides as gene carrier to retinal cells has not been investigated so far to the best of our knowledge.

Taking into account all the above-mentioned considerations, we herein explore the use of lipo-OAAs based on succinyl-tetraethylene pentamine (Stp) building blocks as DNA-binding molecules with potential application in ocular gene delivery *via* the treatment of retinal cells. The selected lipopeptides contain lysines, histidines, tyrosines and cysteines and they were synthesized *via* solid-phase peptide synthesis. Complexes were formed by electrostatic interaction with plasmid DNA and characterized using the resources of dynamic light scattering, cryo-TEM and agarose gel electrophoresis. The cell cytotoxicity and transfection efficiency were further evaluated in ARPE-19 and HeLa cells. The correlation between the chemical nature of the lipo-OAAs and the structural features of the lipopolyplexes with the biological outputs is herein discussed, thus allowing the identification of favorable structural motifs and the most suitable lipo-OAA for gene delivery particularly to retinal cells.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Chemicals

Linear polyethyleneimine (LPEI, $M_w = 25$ kDa) was purchased from Polysciences, Inc. Protected Fmoc- α -amino acids (99 %), 2-chlorotrityl chloride resin, *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, peptide grade), *N,N*-diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA, 98%), piperidine (99%), 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP, peptide grade), and trifluoroacetic acid (TFA, peptide grade) were purchased from Iris Biotech (Marktredwitz, Germany). Triisopropylsilane (TIS, 98%), 1-hydroxybenzotriazole (HOBt, 98%), 1,2-ethanedithiol (EDT, 98%), hydrazine monohydrate (98%), di-*tert*-butyl dicarbonate (Boc₂O or Boc anhydride, 99%) were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich (Munich, Germany). Dichloromethane (DCM, 99.8%), methanol (MeOH, 99.9%), acetonitrile (99.9%) and hydrochloric acid solution 1M (HCl) were purchased from Bernd Kraft (Duisburg, Germany), methyl *tert*-butyl ether (MTBE, 99%) was acquired from Brenntag GmbH (Essen, Germany) and *n*-hexane (95%) was purchased from Grüssing GmbH (Filsum, Germany). Benzotriazol-1-yl-oxy tripyrrolidinophosphonium hexafluorophosphate (Pybop, 98%), 2-(1H-benzotriazol-1-yl)-1,1,3,3-tetramethyluronium hexafluorophosphate (HBTU) and syringe microreactors were obtained from MultiSynTech (Witten, Germany). Deionized water was purified in-house using Evoqua Ultra Clear® Glass Panel Systems (Günzburg, Germany). Fmoc-Stp(Boc₃)-OH building block was synthesized in-house at LMU Munich.^{49,50} Kaiser test solution: 80 % (*w/v*) phenol in EtOH; 5 % (*w/v*) ninhydrine in EtOH and 20 μ M KCN in pyridine (2 mL of 1 mM KCN (aq) in 98 mL of pyridine)⁵¹ were also prepared in-house. Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium/Nutrient Mixture F-12 with GlutaMAX™ (DMEM:F12 GlutaMAX) medium, FBS, penicillin/streptomycin and MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) were acquired from Thermo Fisher Scientific Brazil (São Paulo, Brazil). The plasmid pEGFP-N1 (Clontech Laboratories, United States) containing the early promoter of HCMV and the enhanced green fluorescent protein

(GFP) gene was amplified in competent *Escherichia coli* and purified by using a PureLink™ HiPure Plasmid Maxiprep (Invitrogen™, United States) kit. The purity of the DNA was confirmed by UV absorbance at 260/280 nm.

Synthesis of the Lipopeptides and Manufacturing of the Lipopolyplexes

The lipopeptides were synthesized and characterized by ¹H-NMR and MALDI-TOF MS as previously described (LP1 - referred as 1198,⁴⁶ LP2 - referred as 1208 and LP3 - referred as 1211,⁴⁷ and LP4 - referred as 1214⁴⁸). The lipopolyplexes were produced using 500 ng of pEGFP-N1 plasmid DNA (pDNA) diluted in HEPES buffer and different amounts of the oligomers to reach desired protonatable oligomer nitrogen (N) to nucleic acid phosphate (P) N/P ratios into a final volume of 200 μL. The solutions were quickly mixed and incubated for 40 min at room temperature under stirring (300 rpm).

Characterization of the Lipopolyplexes

Agarose Gel Electrophoresis: Agarose gel 1% (w/v) for pDNA analysis was prepared by dissolving agarose in TBE buffer (1.5 g of agarose in 150 mL of TBE buffer 1x) followed by the addition of GelRed® (Biotium, Hayward, United States). The lipopolyplexes containing 100 ng of pDNA (pEGFP-N1) were loaded into the wells after adding 4 μL of loading buffer (6 mL of glycerine, 1.2 mL of 0.5 M EDTA, 2.8 mL of H₂O, 0.02 g of bromophenol blue). The experiments were performed at 120 V for 60 min, and the results were recorded by using a UV transilluminator (Dark Hood DH-40, Biostep, Burkhardtsdorf, Germany).

Particle Size and Surface Charge Measurements: Particle size and zeta (ζ) potential measurements were performed using a Zetasizer Nano ZS apparatus (Malvern Instruments, Worcestershire, U.K.). In the dynamic light scattering mode, the lipopolyplexes (500 μL

solution containing 5 μg of pDNA) were measured with a flexible attenuator at 173°. The refractive index of the solvent was fixed at 1.33 and its viscosity at 0.8872 mPa.s. Samples were measured five times with three sub runs of 30 s counting time. For ζ -potential measurements, the samples were diluted by the addition of 500 μL of NaCl 20 mM and measured five times with 20 sub-runs.

Cryo-Transmission Electron Microscopy (Cryo-TEM): The cryo-TEM measurements were conducted at the Brazilian Nanotechnology National Laboratory (LNNano). The samples for cryo-TEM imaging were prepared at 22 °C and 100 % relative humidity in a controlled environment vitrification system (FEI Vitrobot). Three- μL of the samples were loaded into a lacey carbon film (300 mesh) supported on a copper TEM grid. The excess of the liquid samples was removed by blotting with filtering paper grade 595 (Ted Pella). The grids were then immediately plunged into liquid ethane. The TEM grids were previously submitted to a glow discharge system (glow time 50 s, glow charge - 25 mA). The specimens were stored in liquid nitrogen and then transferred under controlled conditions into an autoloader cassette. The autoloader was transferred to the microscopic column and the temperature was kept at -182 °C during these procedures. The images were acquired on a Talos F200C (Thermo Fisher Scientific) high-resolution TEM at accelerating voltage of 200 kV equipped with a Ceta 16M 4K CMOS imaging camera (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and a TEM Imaging & Analysis version 4.21 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) software. The images were recorded in the low dose imaging mode to reduce electron-beam radiation-damage.

Biological Assays

Cell Culture: Arising retinal pigment epithelial (ARPE-19) and HeLa cells were grown in DMEM:F12 GlutaMAX medium supplemented with 10 % FBS, 100 $\text{U}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ penicillin and

100 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ streptomycin. The cells were cultured in ventilated flasks in a cell incubator at 37 °C and 5 % CO_2 atmosphere.

Cell Viability: The cytotoxicity of the lipopolyplexes was probed by using the MTT assay. ARPE-19 and HeLa cells (20000 cells/well) were seeded 24 hs prior the experiments in 96-well plates and afterwards treated with 80 μL of fresh medium. The cells were incubated with 0.5 μg of the plasmid pEGFP-N1 (20 μL of lipopolyplex solutions into 80 μL of fresh DMEM medium) followed by the incubation time of 48 hs at 37 °C. Subsequently, 10 μL (5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) of MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) was added to each well. After 2 hs of incubation time, unreacted dye and medium were removed, and the 96-well plates were stored at - 80 °C for at least 30 min. To dissolve the purple formazan product, 100 μL of DMSO was added per well and the plate was incubated for 30 min at 37 °C under gentle stirring. Each well was quantified by measuring the absorbance at 570 nm using a Synergy HTX microplate reader (Biotek, Winooski, United States). All experiments were performed in triplicate. The cell viability (%) was calculated relative to control wells treated with Hepes. The experimental data are reported as mean \pm standard deviation.

Evaluation of Transfection Efficiency: The luciferase assay kit for gene transfection, pCAGGS (Promega Co.), containing the luciferase gene was used to quantitatively evaluate transfection rates. ARPE-19 and HeLa cells (20000 cells/well) were seeded for 24 hs prior the experiments in 96-well plates. Transfection efficiency of the lipopeptides was evaluated using 0.5 μg (10 μL of lipopolyplexes in 190 μL of medium) of the plasmid pCAGGS-Luc. The cells were treated with polyplexes for 48 hs. Afterwards, the medium was removed and the cells were lysed in 40 μL of lysis buffer. Then, 100 μL of the luciferase assay reagent (E4550) was added to each well and the luminescence was measured in a luminometer plate reader. The

total protein amount was determined by using a Micro BCATM (Pierce, Rockford, IL) protein assay kit. The values (experiments were performed in triplicate) of transfection efficiency are reported as relative light units per mg of protein (RLU/mg protein).

Complementary, the gene expression was qualitatively observed by fluorescence microscopy. The ARPE-19 and HeLa cells were seeded into 96-well plates at a density of 20000 cells/well in the cell culture medium and incubated at 37 °C in CO₂ atmosphere for 24 hs. Afterwards, the medium was replaced by 200 µL of fresh DMEM containing lipopolyplexes (0.5 µg of the plasmid pEGFP-N1 in 10 µL lipopolyplexes solutions) followed by an incubation time of 48 hs. The images were acquired on a widefield Leica DMI 6000 B microscope (Leica Microsystems, Germany) coupled to an ultrafast Leica DFC365 FX digital camera (Leica Microsystems, Germany). The L5 (ex. 460-500 nm, DC 505 nm, em. 512-542 nm) cube filters were selected. The images were processed using the LAS X software (Leica).

Statistical Analysis: The statistical significance of experiments was evaluated by using the Turkey test, $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant in all analyses (95 % confidence interval).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis of the Lipopeptides and Manufacturing of the Lipopolyplexes

Lipopeptides, which showed highly favorable biological properties in previous studies,⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ were selected and synthesized *via* solid-phase assisted synthesis (SPPS). The transfecting agents comprise succinoyl tetraethylene pentamine (Stp) building blocks, α -lysines, histidines, fatty acids as the hydrophobic component, and stabilizing tyrosine trimers. Some of the sequences (the ones named LP1 and LP4) were synthesized with terminal cysteines. The Table 1 provides the characteristics of the T-shaped structures, and their architectures are illustrated in Figure 1. The detailed chemical structures of all the compounds are given in Figure S1 and analytical data are provided in Figures S2-S6 (Supporting Information File).

Table 1. Chemical features of the synthesized lipopeptides.

Entry	Mw free base	Protonable amines (N)	Sequence
LP1	3228.2	13	K(N ₃)-C-Y ₃ -Stp ₂ -K(K(OleA) ₂)-Stp ₂ -Y ₃ -C
LP2	3021.9	13	K(N ₃)-Y ₃ -Stp ₂ -K(K(OleA) ₂)-Stp ₂ -Y ₃
LP3	5478.7	25	K(N ₃)-Y ₃ -(H-Stp) ₄ -H-K(K(OleA) ₂)-H-(Stp-H) ₄ -Y ₃
LP4	4051.0	13	K(N ₃)-C-Y ₃ -(H-Stp) ₂ -H-K(K(OleA) ₂)-H-(Stp-H) ₂ -Y ₃ -C

Figure 1. Molecular architectures of the synthesized T-shaped lipopeptides.

These sequences are readily soluble in buffered aqueous solution and the pure compounds (not complexed with DNA) have hydrodynamic diameter $D_H \sim 6$ nm suggesting that they do not self-assemble themselves (not shown here for brevity) possibly due to their T-shaped architecture and relatively low hydrophobic volume fraction.

The lipopolyplexes were formed by mixing pEGFP-N1 plasmid DNA (pDNA) and different amounts of the oligomers to reach desired protonatable nitrogen (lipopeptide) to phosphate (pDNA) molar ratios (N/P). The DNA-binding capacity of the synthesized lipopeptides has been probed by agarose gel electrophoresis. The gel retardation assays for the whole set of lipopeptides as a function of the N/P ratio are provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Agarose gel electrophoresis of lipopolyplexes produced using LP1, LP2, LP3 and LP4 at different N/P ratios according to the labels (free pDNA was used as the control).

The agarose gel electrophoresis data evidence DNA-binding and complexation. The profiles are similar and pDNA condensation seems to be not fully reached up to $N/P = 3$. Nevertheless, the lipopeptides can condense the nucleic acids at $N/P \geq 6$, regardless of their chemical features. The investigated oligomers have at least two stabilizing components in their composition (oleic acid modification and tyrosine trimers in LP2 and LP3, or both further combined with terminal cysteines in LP1 and LP4). Accordingly, the experimental data suggest that the introduction of cysteines in the chemical structure of the oligomers does not seem to provide further stabilization to the assemblies since all the investigated structures are able to efficiently compact pDNA at similar N/P range. Therefore, although the presence of cysteines is highly relevant in stabilizing siRNA, which contains fewer negative charges compared to pDNA,⁴⁹ thus attenuating oligomer-nucleic acid electrostatic interactions, the herein reported

data underlines that their presence is not critical for the compaction and stabilization of pDNA-based lipopolyplexes.

The electrostatic complexes were further characterized by dynamic and electrophoretic light scattering, and the quantitative data are provided in Table 2. The experimental results show that the produced lipopolyplexes have a hydrodynamic diameter ranging roughly from 50 to 130 nm depending on the chemical features of the lipopeptide, and on the N/P ratio. The hydrodynamic diameter and PDI values are in the same range reported previously for lipopolyplexes produced using similar oligomers.^{24,47} The size of the lipopolyplexes is reduced as N/P ratio increases, thereby suggesting higher degrees of compaction. The surface charge of the assemblies is positive, ranging from + 13 to + 21 mV. The positive charge indicates overcompensation of the negative charges of the nucleic acids as a result of the excess of lipopeptides forming the electrostatic complexes. The largest lipopolyplexes were produced from LP3, although the differences are only moderate. Nevertheless, the size, as well as the surface charge of all the electrostatic complexes are similar at higher N/P ratios.

Table 2. Hydrodynamic diameter (D_H), polydispersity index (PDI) and ζ -potential values for lipopolyplexes produced using the T-shaped lipopeptides LP1, LP2, LP3 and LP4.

Entry	N/P	D_H (nm)	PDI	ζ (mV)
LP1	6	91 ± 13	0.17	$+ 21 \pm 1$
	12	69 ± 4	0.18	$+ 19 \pm 3$
	20	54 ± 9	0.15	$+ 20 \pm 1$
LP2	6	81 ± 1	0.17	$+ 16 \pm 1$
	12	68 ± 4	0.15	$+ 19 \pm 2$
	20	59 ± 4	0.17	$+ 18 \pm 1$
LP3	6	129 ± 6	0.16	$+ 13 \pm 1$
	12	84 ± 3	0.16	$+ 15 \pm 1$
	20	56 ± 5	0.20	$+ 14 \pm 1$
LP4	6	65 ± 3	0.14	$+ 15 \pm 1$
	12	57 ± 7	0.17	$+ 20 \pm 1$
	20	61 ± 7	0.16	$+ 17 \pm 2$
LPEI	6	99 ± 14	0.21	$+ 23 \pm 1$
	12	67 ± 8	0.21	$+ 30 \pm 3$
	20	61 ± 7	0.20	$+ 35 \pm 4$

The light scattering data agree reasonably well with the previously reported and discussed agarose gel electrophoresis assays. They confirm that the incorporated cysteine domains also do not have a pronounced influence on particle size and surface charge of the manufactured assemblies. In general, the DLS data did not indicate the presence of large aggregates. All synthesized lipopeptides contain two lipophilic oleic acids attached to the backbone. Their presence was indeed previously shown to assist complex stabilization and endosomal escape.²⁴ The results suggest that the presence of the tyrosine trimers and the

relatively long carbon chains in oleic acid contribute to the formation of fairly small and stable nanoparticles even in the absence of cysteines. Overall, the combination of agarose gel electrophoresis, dynamic light scattering and ζ -potential measurements robustly confirm that the lipopeptides are able to properly compact pDNA at $N/P \geq 6$ into relatively small and positively charged assemblies.

The shape of the produced supramolecular structures was further probed by cryo-TEM and the images are reported in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Cryo-TEM micrographs of (a) LP1/DNA, (b) LP2/DNA, (c) LP3/DNA and (d) LP4/DNA lipopolyplexes produced at $N/P = 12$.

The experimental data suggest the presence of electrodense structures in cryo-TEM (lipopolyplexes) with a spherical or nearly spherical morphology. The images highlight that the assemblies are fairly compact with about 100 nm in size, which is compatible with the values of hydrodynamic diameters determined by DLS. Indeed, the values of polydispersity index determined by DLS range from 0.10 to 0.20 and suggest that there is a certain degree of heterogeneity in the overall dimension of the supramolecular assemblies. Therefore, the provided stability and positive surface charge prevent the aggregation of particles, thus resulting in the formation of fairly homogenous assemblies. Additional cryo-TEM images are given in the Supporting Information File (Figure S7).

Evaluation of Cell Toxicity

The cytotoxicity of the lipopolyplexes was evaluated in two different cell lines: ARPE-19 and HeLa cells. The experimental data are reported in Figure 4. The MTT assays demonstrated that, particularly in the case of ARPE-19 cells, the cytotoxicity promoted by the electrostatic complexes is dose-dependent, and the metabolic activity is reduced when relatively high amounts of the transfecting agents are present. This trend is not clearly observed with HeLa cells, which indicates that ARPE-19 cells are more sensitive. This is clearly observed in the case of LPEI polyplexes since strongly reduced metabolic activity becomes obvious at N/P = 6. According to the ISO 10993-5:2009, which describes test methods to assess the *in-vitro* cytotoxicity of biomaterials, cytotoxic effects are considered when cell viability is reduced by more than 30% compared to the control. The dotted lines in Figure 4 refer to the value of 70% cell viability.

Figure 4. Viability of ARPE-19 (A) and HeLa (B) cells in contact for 24 hs with lipopolyplexes produced at different N/P ratios according to the labels (the results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation; LPEI was used for comparison purposes). Statistical analysis in comparison with the LPEI polyplexes at same N/P ratio, ns: no significant difference, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$. Data are shown as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$).

The reason for the different tolerability of transfections by individual cell lines is not clear, although it might be related to structural and metabolic differences of the living systems. HeLa is a cancer cell line which to some extent explains the higher resistance, whereas ARPE-19 cells originate from the retinal pigment epithelium and therefore, it is supposed to be more sensitive. Nevertheless, according to the ISO 10993-5:2009 definition, all transfections with lipoplexes in the evaluated concentration range can be considered non-toxic to both cell lines (cell viability always higher than 70%).

Evaluation of Transfection Rates

The transfection efficiency provided by the lipopeptides was similarly investigated with respect to both cell lines, and the experimental data are provided in Figure 5. The lipopolyplexes produced from lipopeptides LP2 and LP3 are evidenced to transfect cells more efficiently compared to LP1 and LP4. Indeed, the lipopolyplexes based on LP2 generally provided the highest levels of luciferase expression regardless of the cell line, whereas the ones containing terminal cysteines showed lower efficiency. This is more clearly observed in HeLa cell transfection. The histidine modification of transfecting agents has been shown to typically enhance gene transfer due to the intracellular protonation of the imidazole group ($pK_a \sim 6.0$)^{29,50,51} nevertheless, in the current investigation the lipopeptides LP2 and LP3 were evidenced to provide similar performances.

Figure 5. *In-vitro* luciferase expression in ARPE-19 (A) and HeLa (B) cells after 48 hs of incubation with lipopolyplexes at various N/P ratios according to the labels (the results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, LPEI was used for comparison purposes). Statistical analysis in comparison with the LPEI polyplexes at same N/P ratio, ns: no significant difference, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$. Data are shown as mean \pm SD (n = 3).

Accordingly, the experimental data suggest that the proton sponge effect might not be the main driving force governing endosomal escape as a direct comparison of analog structures with and without histidine moieties do not show remarkable differences. Truly, calculations previously demonstrated that the osmotic pressure generated by the proton sponge effect is not sufficient to solely conduct to the endosome lysis process,¹⁸ and other contributions have to be taken into account. Direct complex-endosomal membrane interaction to explain the endosomal escape has been proposed.^{52,53} In this regard, the incorporation of lipid moieties into cationic oligomers may notably enhance the lytic activity and membrane destabilization *via* hydrophobic interactions, thus significantly contributing to the escape of the lipopolyplexes. Furthermore, the interaction of free polycations (not complexed) with lipid bilayers were also proposed as an important driving force to promote gene transfection.⁵⁴ Hence, the endosomal escape is presumably mediated by a combination of osmotic-pressure-induced membrane rupture, aided by the presence of free polycations which play an important role by interacting and destabilizing the lipid membranes. The main driving force, nevertheless, seems to be still debatable due to the current contradictory reports.⁵⁵

The presence of terminal cysteines (LP1 and LP4) appears to attenuate the transfection efficiency to some extent. This might be associated with enhanced polyplex stabilization provided by the presence of the terminal domains *via* the bioreversible disulfide cross-links. Accordingly, relatively lower stability seems to be beneficial to increase the transfection rates. Therefore, after reaching a certain threshold stability which appears to be already properly provided by the presence of the tyrosine trimers and oleic acid domains, adding further components for stabilization purposes might hamper the pDNA unpacking in the cytosol and the further intranuclear delivery. Hence, clearly a stability-lability balance has to be taken into account to optimize the transfection efficiency for such type of assembly. Despite the structural differences of the lipopolyplexes, they are all more efficient than LPEI to induce transgene

expression. The pDNA gene transfer activity is observed to be at least hundred-fold improved, exceeding the standard LPEI.

The lipopolyplexes produced using the lipopeptides LP2 and LP3 are more effective in transfecting ARPE-19 cells at $N/P = 12$ compared to $N/P = 20$. This possibly reflects a slightly higher effects on cell viability with increasing N/P as evidenced in the experimental data reported in Figure 4. Overall, the low cytotoxicity and the higher luciferase levels observed, particularly for LP2 and LP3, highlight the potential application of such transfecting agents as gene carriers for gene transfer to retinal cells.

The performance of the lipopolyplexes as gene delivery systems was complementarily evaluated qualitatively by fluorescence microscopy. The cells were incubated with lipopolyplexes produced using pEGFP-N1. The images reported in Figure 6 for ARPE-19 cells and Figure 7 for HeLa cells agree reasonably well with the quantitative data determined by using the luciferase assay.

Figure 6. Bright field and fluorescence images of *in-vitro* EGFP expression in ARPE-19 cells after 48 hs of incubation time as mediated by different lipopolyplexes at various N/P ratios according to the legends (all images were acquired under the same experimental conditions; LPEI was used for comparison purposes).

Figure 7. Bright field and fluorescence images of *in-vitro* EGFP expression in HeLa cells after 48 hs of incubation time as mediated by different lipopolyplexes at various N/P ratios according to the legends (all images were acquired under the same experimental conditions; LPEI was used for comparison purposes).

The images robustly and undoubtedly confirm the higher ability of lipopolyplexes based on LP2 and LP3 to transfect both cell lines. Accordingly, with the large pDNA molecules the presence of terminal cysteines is not required for stable polyplex formation and the combination of tyrosine and oleic acid motifs is optimal to induce high gene transfer activity.

Although the images visually highlight higher gene expression in HeLa compared to ARPE-19 cells, which can be expected since human retinal pigment epithelial are known to be a hard-to-transfect cell,^{43,56,57} the herein reported quantitative experimental data underlines that the investigated oligomers enable efficient ARPE-19 cell transfection and accordingly, they might lead to relevant benefits in the formulation of vehicles for genetic nanomedicines targeting ocular diseases.

CONCLUSIONS

In this investigation, lipopeptides containing succinoyl tetraethylene pentamine (Stp) building blocks, α -lysines, histidines, fatty acids, tyrosine trimers and cysteine domains were selected for gene transfer into human cervix carcinoma HeLa and retinal pigment epithelial ARPE-19 cells. The chosen sequences were previously demonstrated to have highly favourable biological properties,⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ and we herein reveal DNA condensation at $N/P \geq 6$ into fairly compact spheres with size ranging from 50-130 nm as evidenced by cryo-TEM and DLS. The biological evaluations (cell viability, luciferase assay and GFP fluorescence microscopy) highlight that the lipopolyplexes fulfil the most relevant requirements (efficient intracellular pDNA delivery and low toxicity) for a potential gene delivery vector. Highly relevant, the experimental data underline that two polyplex stabilizing components (fatty acids and tyrosine domains) are sufficient to efficiently provide pDNA condensation, and the addition of a further component (terminal cysteine domains) possibly leads to exceeding stability which attenuates the intracellular pDNA unpacking. This behavior indeed depends on the type, size and surface

charge of the nucleic acid since cysteine domains were earlier demonstrated to be relevant to stabilize siRNA.⁴⁹ Truly, ocular gene therapies seem to gain momentum and expanding the library of nonviral gene delivery platforms is of due relevance as the vector choice depends on the delivery route, on the disease and transgene, as well as target location and cell type. We demonstrate that these lipopeptide sequences are efficient to transfect human retinal pigment epithelial cells which are known to be hard-to-transfect cells.^{43,56,57} Accordingly, they might lead to relevant benefits in the development of strategies towards helping gene replacement and editing therapies envisaging novel technologies for ocular treatments based on retinal delivery.

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